

Studies in Physico-Chemical Properties of Caseins: Part. II. Sorption of Water Vapour by Caseins

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Sorption isotherms of water at 30° on different samples of casein isolated by different methods from cows' milk and buffalos' milk have been studied and the data interpreted in the light of BET and Harkins-Jura equations. The values of specific surface area obtained by both the methods are in fairly good agreement keeping in view the differences in the postulates involved. The values of V at 0.18 r.v.p. is close to V_m of BET equation and this enables calculation of surface area of caseins from a single point on the isotherm.

It appears that sorption of water proceeds initially at the sites provided by ionic groups and then by non-ionic polar groups of the side-chains and that one molecule of water is attached per polar group. Thereafter begins further condensation of water molecules not only on the above mentioned sites, but also inside the polypeptide skeleton forming casein solution. This causes weakening of the peptide bonds leading to denaturation and putrefaction of the casein.

A good deal of literature on the sorption of water vapour by proteins has been published in recent years¹⁻⁷. However, comparatively few experimental data on caseins⁸⁻⁹, and, in particular, on caseins obtained from different sources and by employing different methods of isolation, are available. The importance of such data as a possible tool for the estimation of surface areas, apparent or real, of proteins has been rightly stressed^{5,9}. The problem is also of interest in revealing possible interaction of polar molecules of water with a number of polar groups, ionic as well as non-ionic, and peptide linkages in the casein molecule. Bull's data⁵, as interpreted by Pauling¹⁰, indicate that the peptide bonds show little attraction for water molecules since these are held together by hydrogen bonding to such an extent that residual attraction for water is negligible. However, the work of Mellon *et al.*¹¹ indicates that adsorption of water vapour by peptide bonds, from 2-6 units in length, is possible. It is the purpose of this paper to report the sorption isotherms of water vapour obtained by us on a series of caseins separated from milk by five different methods and to attempt a possible interpretation of the data.

1. D. D. Eley and R. B. Leslie, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 1002.
2. D. D. Eley, *Advan. Chem. Phys.* (Interscience), 1964, **7**, 238.
3. Jerrold, M. Seehof, Bertram Keilin and Sidney W. Benson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2427.
4. A. D. McLaren and John W. Rowen, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1951, **7**, 289.
5. H. B. Bull, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1499.
6. Bernard Katchman and A. D. McLaren, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 2124.
7. Sidney W. Benson, David A. Ellis and Robert W. Zwanzing, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2102.
8. Edward F. Mellon, Alfred H. Korn, Elsie L. Kokes and Sam R. Hoover, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1870.
9. R. W. Green, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, (New Zealand), 1949, **77**, 313.
10. L. Pauling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 555.
11. E. F. Mellon, A. H. Korn and S. R. Hoover, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3040.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : Ten samples of casein were prepared, 5 from cows' milk and 5 from buffalos' milk, one sample of each variety was prepared by each one of the following methods :

By (i) the addition of Rennet, (ii) the use of ultracentrifuge, (iii) Hammersten method, (iv) Zoller method, and (v) Van Slyke-Bosworth method.

The details of these methods were given in the previous paper (Part I) of the present series^{12a}.

Water adsorption isotherms : The water adsorption isotherms were obtained at 30° (± 0.2) by using the vacuum desiccator technique described earlier by Puri *et al.*¹³. The equilibrium was attained generally after 4 to 10 days, the period increasing with increase in the relative vapour pressure. The caseins were found to suffer decomposition, as indicated by decrease in weight and development of odour, if the samples were allowed to stand in atmospheres of 94 per cent and 98 per cent relative humidities for periods longer than 10 days.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The adsorption isotherms on the various samples of casein, isolated from cows' milk, are plotted in fig. 1. The isotherms for the corresponding samples separated from buffalo milk had essentially the same features, although the sorption values were slightly low.

Fig. 1 : Water adsorption isotherms of cows' casein.

The isotherms appear to be of type II of the well known classification of adsorption isotherms, indicating formation of multimolecular layers. There is no evidence for capillary condensation.

12. O. L. Sponsler, J. D. Bath and J. W. Ellis, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1940, **44**, 996.

12a. B. R. Puri, K. K. Toteja and R. C. Malik. *This Journal* 1968, **45**, 889.

13. B. R. Puri, M. L. Lakhanpal and Balvir Verma, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 841,

The B.E.T. plots of $x/V(1-x)$ against x (where V is the volume of water adsorbed at relative pressure x) give reasonably straight lines (Fig. 2) over 0.05–0.50 relative pressure range. According to B.E.T. equation, the slopes of these lines should give $C-1/V_m C$ and intercepts give $1/V_m C$, where V_m is the index of surface, being the volume required to cover the surface of 100 g. of casein completely as a monolayer and C is a constant given by the equation

$$C = e^{(E_1 - E_l)/RT} \quad (i)$$

where E_1 is the heat of adsorption in the first layer and E_l the heat of liquefaction of the adsorbate.

Fig. 2 : B.E.T. plots of adsorption isotherms of cow's casein.

The values of $E_1 - E_l$ (Table I) are seen to be somewhat higher than those observed in the case of soils¹⁴ and yet not sufficiently high to indicate chemical interaction. It appears that the forces involved are partly physical and partly quasi-chemical in nature, probably involving hydrogen bonding or the like between water molecules and polar groups of caseins.

In an isothermal process involving the transfer of one g. of water from vapour state to the surface of the adsorbent, the free energy change which may be regarded as a quantitative measure of the affinity of the adsorbent for the vapour, assuming the gas law to apply, is given by the equation

$$\Delta F = RT/M \int_0^1 a \frac{dx}{x} \quad (ii)$$

where M is the molecular weight of water and a is the weight of water adsorbed per given weight of dry protein. In order to integrate the equation, a/x was plotted against x (Fig. 5) and the area under the curve was multiplied by RT/M to get the value for the required free

14. B. R. Puri and L. R. Sharma, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, 15, 178.

energy change. These values (Table I), which incidentally are of the same order as reported by Bull⁶ for some other varieties of proteins, are not sufficiently high to indicate any chemical interaction.

The values of V_m , as calculated from the B.E.T. plots are also given in Table I. Assuming that a molecule of water covers 10.5 \AA^2 of surface, the specific surface areas of the various caseins were calculated. These results are included in table I.

The Harkins and Jura plots of $\log x$ against $1/V^2$ according to the equation

$$\log x = B - A/V^2 \quad (iii)$$

(where A and B are constants) are shown in fig. 3. The relationship seems to be valid over an appreciable range of vapour pressure. Thus the data permit of interpretation in accordance with not only B.E.T. equation but also with Harkins and Jura equation.

TABLE I

Specific surface areas of different caseins from moisture adsorption isotherms

Method of preparation	B.E.T. equation		Harkins-Jura equation		ΔF	V_m at 0.18 r.v.p.	Area from V_m at 0.18 r.v.p. $\text{m}^2/\text{g}.$	
	$E_1 - E_i$	V_m	Sp. surface area $\text{m}^2/\text{g}.$	A				Sp. surface area $\text{m}^2/\text{g}.$
<i>Cow's casein</i>								
Rennet	1845	5.30	187	19.1	167	-822	4.50	158
Ultracentrifuge	1817	5.49	193	19.1	165	-844	5.50	193
Hammarsten	2616	5.07	178	20.7	174	-790	5.00	175
Zoller	2870	5.01	176	21.9	172	-844	5.10	179
Van Slyke-Bosworth.	2648	4.76	169	19.5	166	-775	4.90	172
<i>Buffalo's casein</i>								
Rennet	1975	5.13	180	9.8	120	-542	4.92	172
Ultra centrifuge	1960	5.31	186	13.8	142	-560	5.20	182
Hammarsten	2013	4.56	160	19.2	167	-705	4.18	146
Zollar	2964	4.33	152	17.3	159	-744	4.54	159
VanSlyke-Bosworth.	2013	4.56	162	21.1	176	-717	4.70	165

The slope (A) of each curve and specific surface area ($S.S.$) obtained from the equation

$$S.S. = kA^{1/2} \quad (iv)$$

(taking $k = 3.83$) are also included in Table I. The agreement between the values obtained by B.E.T. and Harkins-Jura methods is seen to be sufficiently close. Perhaps it cannot be better, keeping in view the different postulates involved. For example, while B.E.T. method requires knowledge of molecular size of the adsorbate vapour, Harkins-Jura method does not require this value at all.

Fig. 3 : Harkins and Jura plots of adsorption isotherms of cows' casein.

It is also seen that specific surface area of casein separated by means of ultracentrifuge, when it is more or less in its natural state, is a little higher than that of any of the other caseins which were isolated by precipitation methods. It is interesting to note that surface

Fig. 4 : Adsorbed water as a function of V_m at different relative vapour pressures.

area of cows' casein is higher than that of buffalos' casein when the values for the corresponding samples are compared with one another. This may be perhaps one of the factors responsible for greater stability of cows' milk.

Incidentally, the surface areas being reported by us for caseins in this paper are of the same order as reported for some other proteins in the literature^{5,7}.

The plots of V at a fixed relative vapour pressure (0.18, 0.28, or 0.50) against V_m for the vapour samples of casein are seen (fig. 3) to give fairly good straight lines. The significance of these observations is that specific surface areas of caseins can be obtained from single points on their water adsorption isotherms. It can be shown that V at 0.18 relative pressure (marked a_1 on each isotherm in fig. 1) is almost equal to V_m in the case of each sample. Orchiston¹⁵, making use of Bull's data⁵ on a few proteins other than caseins, showed that V at 0.21 r.v.p. is almost equal to V_m .

The values of specific surface area obtained from the values of V at 0.18 r.v.p. are also included in table I (last column) for easy comparison with the values obtained by the other two methods.

It has been suggested^{5,16} that surface areas of proteins obtained from water vapour adsorption isotherm are considerably smaller than the areas as spread in thin films. It appears highly probable that V_m is a measure of the water required to complete the first step in the adsorption process and that this step corresponds to the sorption of one molecule of water per ionic polar group in the side chain. Knowing the number of ionic groups, at least in the case of 3 acid caseins from their titration curves as reported in Part I of the present series^{12a}, it is possible to calculate theoretically the values of V_m assuming that one molecule of water is attached per ionic group. These values along with B.E.T. values are given in table II. The agreement is fairly close and offers support to the view that most of the sorbed water in the initial stages is localised at specific sorption sites provided by ionic groups in the side chains.

TABLE II

Amount of water required to form a monolayer on casein separated by different methods

Method preparation	Cow's casein			Buffalo's casein		
	V_m calculated on the basis of ionic groups	V_m from B.E.T. equation	a^2	V_m calculated on the basis of ionic groups	V_m from B.E.T. equation	a_2
Hammarsten	5.40	5.07	10.60	5.48	4.56	9.40
Zoller	5.68	5.01	11.20	5.36	4.33	10.00
VanSlyke-Bosworth	5.56	5.16	10.90	5.39	4.56	9.95

15. H. D. Orchiston, *Soil Sci.*, 1953, **76**, 453.

16. T. M. Shaw, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1944, **12**, 391.

It also appears from the isotherms (fig. 1) that the sorption of water in excess of V_m (i.e., beyond the point a_1) increases almost linearly with the relative vapour pressure upto a certain limiting value beyond which the curve swings upward rather rapidly. The point at which the isotherm swings upward, denoted by a_2 , can be obtained more accurately by selecting from the plots of a/x against x (fig. 5) the point where a/x is minimum and then multiplying this value by the corresponding value of x . The values of a_2 for the various

Fig. 5 : Plots of a/x against x .

caseins are given in Table II. It is seen that a_2 is almost double of a_1 . It appears that after the completion of sorption of one molecule of water by each ionic group, the process of attachment of one molecule of water to each non-ionic polar group begins. In this connection it may be noted that the numbers of ionic polar and non-ionic polar groups in caseins have been found, by actual analysis¹⁷, to be fairly close to one another, being 267 equiv. and 250 equiv. per 10^5 g. of casein, respectively. According to this view a_2 represents the stage at which all the polar groups, ionic as well as non-ionic, are fully covered by a monolayer of water. Thereafter the curve departs from linearity and assumes an upward swing indicating formation of multilayers. The thickness of the adsorbed layer near the saturation pressure corresponds to 5–6 statistical layers, which agrees well with similar work on some other proteins^{5,9}.

It is quite likely that at a considerably higher vapour pressure casein goes into solution and water is taken up at the peptide bonds as well causing weakening of these bonds leading to denaturation or putrefaction of casein, as was actually observed at 94% and 98% relative humidities.

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